

1KSA Data Access Committee Framework

12 May 2025

Table of Contents

SUMMARY	2
INTRODUCTION	2
1. COMMITTEE STRUCTURE AND COMPOSITION	2
2. OBJECTIVES OF THE COMMITTEE	3
3. ACCESS POLICIES AND GUIDELINES	4
4. MONITORING AND REPORTING	6
5. CONFLICT RESOLUTION	6
6. DEFINITIONS	6
7. REFERENCED DOCUMENTS	6

Summary

This document lays out the framework of the 1KSA Data Access Committee (1KSA-DAC) including committee structure; objectives of the committee; access policies and guidelines; monitoring, compliance and reporting; and conflict resolution. The role of the 1KSA Data Access Committee is to effectively balance data access and data sharing with open science, ethical responsibilities, community involvement, benefit sharing particularly for species with bioeconomy applications; and biodiversity conservation applications.

Introduction

The 1KSA project acknowledges that a great deal of controversy exists internationally over access and benefit sharing of digital sequence information (DSI). Although the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and its Nagoya Protocol aim to ensure fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources, concerns have been raised from some biodiversity-rich countries that the free accessibility of DSI in open access databases could undermine their ability to regulate access to their genetic resources. In opposition to this, many scientists and funding organisations call for open access to sequence data as an essential part of reproducible, innovative Open Science. The CBD COP16 meeting in October 2024 saw the adoption of a decision on the use of DSI, viz. that large companies benefiting from DSI contribute a percentage of their profits or revenues to the 'Cali Fund', aimed at ensuring that benefits are more equitably shared with developing countries (Munoz-Garcia et al 2025. Navigating COP16's digital sequence information outcomes: What researchers need to do in practice. Patterns 6:3, 101208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2025.101208>).

The 1KSA project has aimed through these guidelines to provide a middle path through the DSI controversy, providing an "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" approach. As this discussion around DSI evolves, the 1KSA project reserves the right to modify the 1KSA data access terms of use and the access and policy guidelines of the 1KSA Data Access Committee.

1. Committee Structure and Composition

- Genomics Coordinator (DIPLOMICS): Responsible for overseeing the committee's activities, reviewing applications for data access and ensuring compliance with the framework.
- 1KSA Project Manager (DIPLOMICS): Responsible for reviewing applications for data access, communication with applicants, reporting data applications metrics in DIPLOMICS reports, and tracking data usage and publications.
- Bioinformatics Coordinator (DIPLOMICS): Responsible for reviewing applications for data access, oversee secure storage, data sharing mechanisms, and integrity of genomic data.

- 1KSA Steering Committee Representative (new person elected at the beginning of financial year in April): Responsible for overseeing the committee's activities, reviewing applications for data access and ensuring compliance with the framework
- Ad hoc consultants: Ethics and legal experts, to ensure that the framework abides by the internationally recognised principles of the Convention on Biological Diversity (including the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the CBD's recommendations on the use of digital sequence information), the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES) and the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing. In addition, to ensure that the framework is compliant with the laws of South Africa, including the National Environmental Management Biodiversity act (NEMBA) with the associated Bioprospecting, Access and Benefit-Sharing Regulations (BABS), and the Intellectual Property Rights From Publicly Financed Research and Development Act.
- Ad hoc consultants: Community Representatives (stakeholders from local communities involved in South African biodiversity data collection), to ensure that the access process reflects the interests and rights of South African communities, especially those providing biological samples or contributing to biodiversity research, or traditional knowledge holders.

2. Objectives of the Committee

- **Ensure Ethical Data Use**

The committee's main responsibility is to oversee the fair and responsible use of biodiversity genomic data, ensuring alignment with international standards and South Africa's regulations. This will be balanced with access and benefit sharing principles, and Open Science policies.

- **Transparent Access**

The committee will be guided by the 1KSA Terms and Conditions and the 1KSA Data Management Plan, which will be revised from time to time.

- **Provide Access to 1KSA data**

The 1KSA-DAC will provide access to data, via DIRISA, as detailed in Section 3.

- **Monitor publications making use of 1KSA data**

The 1KSA-DAC will check all publication drafts for acknowledgements as detailed in the 1KSA terms of use, and will monitor publications using 1KSA data, as detailed in Section 3.

3. Access Policies and Guidelines

3.1 Data Access: Sample Contributors

- Once the species card has been published on the 1KSA website, the 1KSA project will automatically provide the relevant pod5, fastq and fasta files to the sample contributor through transfer from DIRISA (see 1KSA Data Management Plan). This is automatically provided on a non-exclusive basis for three years.
- If a collaborator of the sample contributor requests access to the data before the data are publicly available, the collaborator can motivate for access to the data through the data request form on the 1KSA webpage (www.1ksa.org.za/getinvolved).

3.2 Data Access: Data Requests

- Sequenced genomes will be publicized through the publication of 1KSA Species cards on the 1KSA website. Access to the sample data, pod5, fastq and fasta files can be requested by completion of the data request form on the 1KSA web page (www.1ksa.org.za/getinvolved). Researchers at South African institutions can motivate for access to the data through the data request form.
- The 1KSA Data Access Committee will meet on a monthly basis to evaluate data requests made through the 1KSA webpage. Requests for sample information, pod5, fastq and fasta files will be considered. Within three years of data generation, the sample contributor will be consulted for requests specific to the species that they contributed. If the request is agreed to, a 1KSA Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) will be drawn up between the 1KSA project and the data recipient. The terms of use applicable to the transfer and use of the data will be outlined in the DTA. The mechanism for acknowledgment of both the sample contributor and the 1KSA project by the data recipient will be included. The data recipient will not be permitted to publish the raw data provided by 1KSA. The requested data sets, use of the data and expected publication and/or intellectual property products arising out of the data will be detailed in an annexure to the DTA.

3.3 Data Publication and Sharing: Sample Contributors

- For biodiversity species with no anticipated economic value beyond the development of tools for conservation (“1KSA conservation species”), the sample contributor will be expected to upload the files to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) within three years of receipt and/or publication of the species card on the 1KSA web page, using the file name convention outlined in the 1KSA terms of use and Sample Submission form. This makes use of “1KSA project - *Species Name*” as the sample title and “1KSA - Nanopore sequencing and draft genome assembly of *Species Name*” as the project description. ENA allows for an embargo period of a year to the open release of this data. Release of the embargo at the time of publication of the genome assembly will be expected. Currently, ENA only accepts fastq and fasta files, although deposition of pod5 files into ENA is expected in future.

- For biodiversity species with an anticipated economic value (“1KSA bioeconomy species”), the sample contributor is expected to engage with all stakeholders (for example, indigenous knowledge holders, their institution’s technology transfer office, intellectual property consultants) prior to publication and uploading the 1KSA genome assembly data to ENA (as detailed in the section above, for “1KSA conservation species”). If the sample contributor wishes to embargo the release of the data beyond the three year period, they must request permission from the 1KSA-DAC in writing (1KSA@diplomics.org.za), providing reasons for this.
- The 1KSA project reserves the right to upload the 1KSA data sets to ENA after the three year period following publication of the species card has passed, should the sample contributor not do so.
- All publications making use of data generated through the 1KSA project are requested to use the acknowledgement statement listed in the terms of use of the project on the 1KSA web page.
- All draft publications must be submitted to the 1KSA-DAC prior to publication. On a monthly basis, the 1KSA-DAC will review publication drafts by sample contributors. The 1KSA data access committee will check that the 1KSA project has been correctly acknowledged according to the 1KSA terms of use. Specifically the 1KSA-DAC will check that both the data set published on the ENA and the publication acknowledges 1KSA, DIPLOMICS, CHPC, DIRISA and the DSTI. The 1KSA-DAC will track these publications over time using Google Scholar, Web of Science, Scopus and equivalent tools. The number of citations will be recorded and the scientific impact of the genome assembly will be evaluated using citation data, in addition to other metrics.
- 1KSA encourages publications in Open Access Journals and publication of a preprint in bioRxiv.

3.4 Data Publication and Sharing: Data Recipients

- All publications making use of data generated through the 1KSA project are required to use the acknowledgement statement listed in the terms of use of the project on the 1KSA web page.
- In addition, data recipients are requested to acknowledge the sample contributor in all publications arising from analysis of data obtained from 1KSA.
- If the pod5, fastq and fasta files arising from the 1KSA project are not publicly available on ENA at the time of publication, the data recipient may not publish the raw data. If the data have been released to ENA, the publication should cite the data accession numbers on ENA.

3.5 Long-Term Data Storage and Accessibility

The 1KSA-DAC will develop policies that will guide the long-term storage and re-use of the data. Re-use examples include a 1KSA database housed by DIRISA (for embargoed bioeconomy species), under the control of a data access committee; or uploading the data to a South African federated Global Biodiversity Information Facility (SA-GBIF), for re-use of the data linked to other biodiversity records.

4. Monitoring and Reporting

- **Monitoring Use of Data:** The committee will implement systems for tracking data usage. This system will be developed during the monthly meetings from April 2025 to September 2025.
- **Data Access Reporting:** The committee will generate an annual report summarising data access applications and decisions
- **Scientific Impact of 1KSA data:** The committee will also generate an annual scientific impact report detailing the scientific impact of the 1KSA data (number of publications, citations and other forms of publication)

5. Conflict Resolution

- **Dispute resolution:** The committee will develop a process for handling disagreements or complaints
- **Appeals process:** The committee will consider appeals, in situations where access to data is required

This framework can be adapted and refined as the 1KSA project progresses, ensuring that the data access committee effectively balances scientific discovery with ethical responsibilities, community involvement, and biodiversity conservation.

6. Definitions

DIPLOMICS	Distributed PLatform in OMICS
DIRISA	Data Intensive Research Initiative of South Africa
CHPC	Centre for High Performance Computing
1KSA-DAC	1KSA Data Access Committee
DSTI	Department of Science, Technology and Innovation
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive

7. Referenced Documents

- 1KSA Terms of Use v2
- 1KSA Sample Submission Form v2.1
- 1KSA Data Management Plan v2
- Data Transfer Agreement v1

Version history

Version	Date Modified	Significant changes	Changes made by	Next review date
0.1	14-02-2025	Document created and reviewed	S. Murray	
1.0	12-05-2025	Changes incorporated as suggested by DAC, version 1.0	S. Murray	30 April 2026

**This document will be reviewed and revised every 12 months*